

Project CHANGES – Spoke 4

D13 – Implementation of pilot and research studies

– Type C – v1.0

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1. Introduction

Within the research lines of Spoke 4, one of our main goals is to experiment with the use of virtual (energy-efficient) technologies within defined and representative real-case scenarios. In particular, we aim to experiment with them using different museum and art collection templates to design specific case studies, deriving and applying best practices that can be further adapted and reused in institutions and contexts with similar characteristics. The six templates of museums and art collections identified are described as follows:

- Type A – high-density and innovative museum;
- Type B – natural history and scientific museum;
- Type C – widespread art gallery;
- Type D – sites museums with tangible and intangible heritage and landscapes, among those that have either low or no virtual and digital implementations with a particular focus in southern Italy;
- Type E – historical palaces, labelled as museums, among the most important in the Italian heritage context, including UNESCO sites;
- Type F – demo-ethnic-anthropological museums, including rural culture museums (with less than 20,000 visitors per year), anthropological museums and museums of art and popular traditions.

In this deliverable, we describe the outcomes of the work conducted with the cultural heritage institutions we have contacted that are compliant with Type C, with whom we have established collaborative research projects. In particular, we have identified a set of cultural institutions with which we have set up specific research projects to put into practice existing and ad-hoc tools developed to provide a system to be freely reusable in a similar context by other cultural institutions not necessarily involved in the project.

Some of these projects, referred to as “core” case studies, have been conducted in collaboration with companies that provide implementation efforts and institutions that offer domain-specific cultural knowledge and citizen engagement. The companies involved were selected through a public call for applications, supported by the project's funds (i.e., cascade calls). These “core” case studies have also been accompanied by additional *research case studies* aligned with the project templates and goals, which the partners of Spoke 4 have used to experiment with further adoptions of the aforementioned workflow, methodologies and tools within the project's period.

2. "Core" case studies

2.1. PhySol-FHC: PHYGITAL CSAC

Outline clear goals and objectives

Describe the initial situation

The Study Centre and Communication Archive (CSAC) is a research centre of the University of Parma founded in 1968 by Professor Arturo Carlo Quintavalle. From its foundation, it concentrated on assembling a collection of fine art, photography, architectural drawings, design, fashion and graphics, as well as organizing exhibitions and publishing catalogues. Since 2007, it has been based at the Valsereana Abbey, also known as the Charterhouse of Paradigna, just a few kilometres from Parma. It is divided into five sections – Fine Art, Photography, Media, Project, and Visual Arts – containing around 12 million single items. Its institutional task is the collection, conservation, cataloguing and promotion of cultural heritage. In addition, it provides scientific consultancy to support teaching, research and design, and organizes exhibitions. Since May 2015, the CSAC Archives–Museum has presented itself as a multifunctional space, where the Museum areas are integrated with the existing areas of the Archives and the Centre for Research and Education.

Describe the chosen technologies to be implemented

For the core case studies two different technologies were implemented.

The first one is related to 2D and 3D scanning utilizing gigapixel 2.5D scanning and 3D photogrammetry technologies, along with the use of virtual modelling and enjoyment devices, the project Phygital Solutions for Fragile and Hidden Collections (PhySol-FHC) aims to create new exhibition paths with a dual nature: real (tactile paths suitable for visually impaired audiences) and virtual (accessible through immersive visualization and manipulation devices like VR headsets and interactive screens).

The second kind of technology, named T-VedO was implemented by University of Florence, according to the Framework in Figure 2.1.1.

Figure 2.1.1. Framework.

Identify specific challenges and opportunities

The goal of PhySol-FHC is to enhance protective and valorisation actions for the CSAC heritage using cutting-edge digital technologies and collaboration between the OdR and the partnering company. PhySol-FHC is creating an experimental model for the use of the CSAC heritage, coordinated in a synergistic way by the University of Parma and the partner company Basilink Art with the aim of reconciling the research activity (also through the creation of research grants) and implemented with the practical skills in technological development and experimentation. PhySol-FHC intends to develop explanatory media useful for the enjoyment of the collections. The research activities have produced new content and new information relating to the CSAC heritage. The contents are used for promotion activities and to improve accessibility and standards of museum enjoyment.

The goal of T-VedO is to enable the enjoyment of works of art by the blind is to reproduce tactile copies of the work, to facilitate tactile exploration. This is even more important when it comes to paintings, which are inherently not accessible to the blind unless they are transformed into 3D models. 3D model reconstruction starting from 2D images is an ill-posed problem; given a 2D image, there are many possible 3D interpretations, and recovering a unique 3D structure from a single 2D image lacks sufficient constraints. Depth ambiguity, multiple interpretations, scale, and perspective are the main factors influencing the 3D reconstruction. Moreover, in the case of painted scenes, also non-realistic shapes characterize the original image, thus leading to more complexity in the reconstruction. Translating painting scenes and

subjects in 3D models to be manufactured using 3D printing is an effective way to deal with this important topic. Together with the 3D reconstruction of the artworks, a multidisciplinary team of art historians and linguistic experts worked to provide a number of information on a set of case studies.

In fact, for this project, eight works of art were examined, including paintings, sculptures, and photographs, all from the CSAC (Centro Studi e Archivio della Comunicazione). Founded in 1968 by Arturo Carlo Quintavalle, the CSAC is an archive, museum, and research center of the University of Parma, located in the Abbey of Valserena in Paradigna, a district north of Parma.

The preliminary research question that guided our work was the following: how do visitors—both women and men—approach museum panels and captions?

Scientific literature identifies at least three main attitudes: texts are not read at all, or only the titles are skimmed; only content related to each person's personal experience is read; or people find it difficult to read the texts. This last attitude is, of course, the most relevant for the purposes of our investigation. After receiving the information sheet—containing biographical data about the artist and a description of the artwork under examination—the linguists' work focused on a double rewriting of these texts, aimed at making the content accessible and usable for two specific types of audiences. The first version is designed primarily for people with functional illiteracy and a low level of education; the second is addressed to university students not engaged in an artistic field. We envisioned a sort of textual continuum: from maximum simplification to a medium degree of simplification, and finally to a specialist or semi-specialist audience, for whom it is reasonable to use the texts as originally written by art historians.

Before beginning the rewriting, however, we carried out a careful survey of the most relevant linguistic phenomena present in the texts: vocabulary and syntax emerged as the most interesting levels of analysis and the ones on which to focus our attention, though some specific morphological features were also noted. The rewritings, aimed at reducing the excessive technicality of museum language, mainly targeted these levels, following the methodological guidelines found in the literature for creating captions accessible to diverse audiences, while maintaining a popularizing perspective. At the lexical level, we adopted a simplification strategy for specialized terms, replacing technical words or compounds with equivalents belonging to common vocabulary. To support this process, we used the GRADIT, the Grande dizionario italiano dell'uso by Tullio De Mauro, which classifies Italian words according to their frequency of use and gathers all the words belonging to the so-called "basic vocabulary." This vocabulary is in turn divided into three tiers: fundamental, high-use, and high-availability, comprising the lemmas that native speakers with an average level of education are expected to know. Regarding morphology, attention focused on

the use of the active voice (as opposed to the passive) and on employing explicit verb forms, favoring them over the infinitive, gerund, and participle. Finally, at the syntactic level, we preferred single-clause sentences and parataxis, seeking to break down constructions that involved second-level subordination.

Consider the potential effects on the involved stakeholders (e.g., museums, local public bodies)

The digital objects obtained through 2D and 3D scanning processes have the function of making art objects hidden due to fragility accessible to visitors of the CSAC and become both cataloguing tools and virtual exhibition objects. Thus, the project on the one hand realizes a cataloguing process of the selected artworks, also realizing the digital infrastructure related to the catalogue, and on the other hand employs the digital objects obtained through the scans to create a virtual exhibition route, usable through the VR viewers and interactive screens.

Digital objects have the function not only of making hidden physical objects accessible to all, but also of expressing the importance of the archive as a place for preserving the witnesses of our civilization, through a narrative that stimulates curiosity and wonder, and therefore emotional participation which generates a sense of closeness and familiarity with the archive itself, normally considered a closed, inaccessible and boring place. Finally, it is intended to co-participate in promotional activities in the local, national and international territory, thus increasing the Centre's notoriety as a laboratory of innovative solutions for future museum fruition.

A significant result of the project was the creation of Visionaria – digital archive of communication, an integrated system for the digital enhancement of the fragile cultural heritage of the CSAC, an experimental model of a "digital" archive, built at the intersection between the physical and digital worlds, with the aim of overcoming the structural limitations of traditional use of cultural and archival heritage. This platform, despite the physical closures that the Centre occasionally experiences due to problems related to its usability, allows direct interaction with digitized works that are not normally on display, thus overcoming physical, geographical, and economic barriers: the CSAC is now an open, public, and shared archive, capable of communicating with a global and multilingual audience.

Describe knowledge sharing among project participants

Illustrate the training activities for the staff of the winning companies (e.g., seminars, workshops)

The ultimate goal of the project is to design an experimental model for cataloguing and utilising the CSAC heritage, coordinated synergistically by the University of Parma

in collaboration with Basilink Art, in an attempt to reconcile the research activities carried out by the recipients of the early-stage researchers in art history, metadata and coordination for cultural activities with the development of practical skills through technological innovations provided by the partner. In this regard, the project has placed particular emphasis on the training of Italian and foreign students specialising in cultural heritage (first and second level graduates, PhD students and PhD holders), promoting the acquisition of diverse skills consistent with the objectives of the National Digitisation Plan. The initiative aimed to contribute to the training of a new generation of cultural heritage professionals, destined to work in both the public administration and the private sector.

Explain the exchange of knowledge by the winning companies regarding how the chosen technologies work and how to use them

All activities were accompanied by a structured technical training plan for grants recipients. The content included:

- advanced use of 2D and 3D digitization tools;
- metadata compliant with ICCD and IIF standards;
- management of local and remote servers;
- publication on interoperable and accessible environments.

Among the most significant results was the collaborative development of a Python script dedicated to the automatic generation of IIF manifests, with a simplified interface for non-programmers. This tool allows the serialization of IIF resources from visual datasets, automating the generation of JSON structures and improving the operational efficiency of staff. The technical team also created a shared document repository containing guidelines, tutorials, templates, and models to ensure replicability and internal continuity.

Another important result is the creation of a number of AI-based tools for 3D reconstruction from the 2D images of paintings. In fact, AI-based methods, and especially CNNs-based ones, seem promising in speeding up the reconstruction phase, providing models that are easily manipulable by CAD experts to retrieve a more dependable model resembling the original artwork.

This could lead to an increase of 3D printed artworks starting from paintings, thus allowing more blind persons to explore them in a novel manner. Moreover, the 3D model can be used to enhance the fruition also for normal-sighted people, e.g. by implementing VR/AR devices. Finally, the models can be stored in digital catalogues and serve the purpose of further CNNs training. Therefore, it is expected that more research will be carried out in the future on the integration of bottom-up approaches (i.e., pixel-level reconstruction based on geometric and photometric cues) with top-

down approaches (i.e., recognition, classification, and retrieval). A more coherent depth in 3D reconstructions can be further improved by improvements within self-supervised learning methods and/or monocular depth estimation. Models that learn either from unlabelled data or by exploiting multi-view geometry without explicit ground truth are more likely to lead to a deeper depth understanding here. Another venue of interest is related to the development of style-aware 3D reconstruction techniques that will rebuild not only the geometric form but also the artistic style of the painting by including brush strokes, shadings, and other artistic deformations. Finally, smarter interactive tools by which users can refine, and fine-tune 3D models could emerge in the near future. Such tools may use AI-driven suggestions, along with user feedback, in an iterative refinement of model quality toward precise reconstructions with reduced user intervention.

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

Detail the digitalisation processes

The adoption of the IIIF (International Image Interoperability Framework) standard represents one of the most significant and strategic technical choices of the Visionaria project. IIIF is an international specification for the publication, interoperability, and advanced use of high-resolution digital objects, adopted by major cultural and academic institutions worldwide. From a technical point of view, the IIIF standard allows:

- progressive viewing of HD images with multi-level dynamic zoom;
- the creation of digital manifests structured according to the Presentation API model;
- the integration of semantic annotations, multilingual metadata, and customized viewing paths;
- interoperability with specialized viewers and research and curation environments.

In Visionaria, the system has been implemented through a server-side infrastructure based on open-source technologies, configured according to RESTful principles and compatible with Presentation API v3 and Image API specifications. The platform has been tested on `mirador.js` and Universal Viewer environments. Due to the current absence of an internal server-side infrastructure at the CSAC, the servers are temporarily hosted and managed by the project's technical partners. The architecture has been designed to be fully migrable, ensuring data portability and integrity. This choice already allows the CSAC digital archive to be positioned within an

interoperable international cultural network in line with FAIR standards for research data.

The digitization of two-dimensional works (sketches, photographs, posters, graphic materials) was carried out using the METIS EDS Alpha planetary scanner, one of the most advanced technologies currently available for the conservative acquisition of fragile documents of high historical and cultural value. The METIS scanner allows:

- acquisition using uniform, diffused LED cold light, without direct contact with the work;
- optical elimination of reflections and distortions thanks to the high-planarity optical system;
- acquisition at calibrated resolution (up to 600 real dpi) with colour fidelity controlled by professional ICC profiles.

The production workflow involved processing images in uncompressed TIFF format, followed by conversion to JPEG2000 for publication via IIIF viewer, and generation of manifests in JSON format according to IIIF Presentation API specifications. All of this was integrated into semantic pipelines based on ICCD vocabularies and text indexing tools. The entire process was also conducted for training purposes, with the active involvement of early-stage researchers in scanner configuration, acquisition parameter optimization, and archival post-production.

Three-dimensional digitization involved the acquisition of a selection of volumetric works using Structure-from-Motion (SfM) photogrammetric pipelines, integrated with 3D models optimized for online exploration and physical production. Activities included:

- photographic calibration with SLR cameras and macro lenses;
- processing with open-source software (Agisoft Metashape, Meshroom);
- retopologization of meshes in Blender and UV texture mapping;
- export to glTF and OBJ formats for the web, and STL for printing. Ten models were selected for FDM printing, using biocompatible PLA and finished with a soft-touch resin coating for tactile enjoyment. Although the reproductions do not yet have Braille labels, the entire route has been designed for independent and inclusive interaction. In the future, it is hoped that tactile information supports, and accessible guidance systems will be integrated, in line with ICOM practices for inclusive museology.

Dealing with the T-VedO project the main steps for the digitalization of data rely on the steps 1-3 depicted in Figure 2.1.1 and reported below.

STEP 1 - Image Acquisition

Acquiring high-resolution images of artworks. For this task it is suggested to use a high-megapixel camera (preferably DSLR, mirrorless, or medium format) with a sharp prime or macro lens. Ensure the artwork is clean and well-lit using high-CRI lights at 45-degree angles to minimize glare. Mount the camera on a sturdy tripod and shoot in RAW format at the camera's highest resolution, using manual focus and a low ISO for maximum detail. For large pieces, capture overlapping sections for stitching later. Post-process the images in software like Lightroom or Photoshop for color correction, sharpening, and exporting to high-quality formats like TIFF.

STEP 2 - Distortion Correction

Correcting distortions introduced by imaging equipment. Several algorithms can be used. Suggested models are the Lens Distortion Model (for radial and tangential correction), Homography Transformation, and Polynomial Warping for geometric distortion correction.

Beyond these classical approaches, advanced calibration and learning-based methods can further enhance accuracy. For example, camera calibration frameworks such as OpenCV's fisheye and omnidirectional models enable precise estimation of complex lens parameters, while bundle adjustment can refine camera poses when multiple images are available. Recent data-driven techniques, including deep convolutional networks for single-image rectification or neural implicit representations, can automatically learn non-linear distortion patterns directly from training data.

STEP 3 - Objects Segmentation

Segmenting objects in the scene and reconstructing perspective using image-processing techniques. If the scene is not characterized by perspective, only segmentation of subjects/objects is required. To accomplish this task, traditional livewire methods can be used. In addition, modern deep-learning-based approaches such as Segment Anything (SAM) provide robust, prompt-driven segmentation that can handle complex or ambiguous boundaries with minimal manual intervention. Other complementary tools include Mask R-CNN or U-Net architectures for pixel-level semantic or instance segmentation, and structure-from-motion (SfM) or multi-view stereo (MVS) pipelines for perspective reconstruction when multiple viewpoints are available.

Illustrate User interface (UI) and user experience (UX) design

A significant part of the project involved the 2D digitization of two-dimensional works, such as drawings, photographs, posters, and graphic materials, which are often

extremely fragile and sensitive to light. These objects were scanned using a professional planetary scanner, which guarantees:

- no direct contact;
- controlled and diffused lighting;
- very high resolution and fidelity to the original details.

This activity also involved the active participation of the early-stage researchers, who were provided with technical know-how related to ICCD standards and conservation practices. The images obtained were then integrated into the ILLF digital archive and made navigable on the Visionaria portal.

At the same time, a second digitization project was launched, dedicated to the 3D scanning of twenty three-dimensional works, selected for their historical value and their physical inaccessibility to the public. These works were acquired using photogrammetry and 3D modelling technologies, processed and optimized to be:

- consultable online with interactive visualization;
- physically reproduced using sustainable 3D printing (ten objects) and used in a new tactile museum tour dedicated to the inclusion of visually impaired people.

Again, the activities had an educational value, involving early-stage researchers and technicians in the management of the acquisition, rendering, and publication process.

One of the most innovative and transformative elements of Visionaria was the development of an immersive Virtual Tour of the entire CSAC, designed to open the doors of the Centre to the whole world. The tour was designed to be accessible in three ways:

- via the Visionaria website, which can be navigated anywhere and by anyone;
- through interactive totems located within the CSAC, which offer an augmented museum experience for physical visitors;
- in virtual reality (VR) mode, using Meta Quest headsets, which allow for an immersive experience from home, schools, or other museums.

This platform does not merely display environments but allows direct interaction with digitized works that are not normally on display. It is possible to explore, zoom in, read metadata, and delve into the objects and the curatorial narrative. This initiative overcomes physical, geographical, and economic barriers. The CSAC, once accessible only to a few specialists, is now an open, public, and shared archive, capable of communicating with a global and multilingual audience.

A central and cross-cutting element of the Visionaria project was the development of a coherent, original and tailor-made visual identity to accompany all the content and digital interfaces created. The graphics were not designed as a simple aesthetic device, but as a functional and integrated visual language capable of enhancing the user experience and cognitive accessibility. The graphic concept was developed internally by the project team, with the aim of:

- creating a recognisable, flexible and modular visual narrative;
- representing in a concise manner the intertwining of the physical and digital dimensions, at the heart of the "figital" concept;
- facilitate the readability and hierarchy of information in web, VR and print environments;
- adapt consistently to the different outputs of the project (IIIF interfaces, virtual tours, physical media, public communication).

The following were designed:

- a specific logo and payoff for the project;
- a functional iconography system for navigation and interactive menus;
- a colour and typographic palette consistent with the cultural and inclusive aims of the project;
- templates for fact sheets, posters, panels, videos and web content. This design component played an essential role in giving all Visionaria project productions a unified, accessible and refined identity.

For what concerns T-VedO project, a number of UIs are created for the purpose of 3D CAD retrieval of subjects and objects in paintings, created starting from the retrieved depth map (see Step 4 in Figure 2.1.1). Moreover, tools for 3D printing of artworks were created. In particular, the retrieved 3D model is saved in a 3D-printable format, usually STL or OBJ and prototyping of accurate physical replicas is performed. In this step it was important to select the 3D printing technology, the material, e.g., PLA, ABS, PETG, to set the layer height (e.g., 0.1 mm) for more detail or thicker layers (e.g., 0.2 mm) for faster prints, to define the internal structure, typically 10–20% for lightweight prints or higher for strength and to enable supports if the model has overhangs or complex geometry.

Outline software programming design

The project was conceived with a modular software programming design, entirely based on open-source technologies to ensure scalability, transparency, and long-

term sustainability. The core of the system is the adoption of the IIIF (International Image Interoperability Framework) standard, which enabled:

- creation of structured manifests compliant with Presentation API v3;
- interoperability with multiple viewers (Mirador.js, Universal Viewer);
- integration of semantic annotations, multilingual metadata, and customised curatorial narratives;
- compatibility with RESTful server-side infrastructures.

A major innovation was the collaborative development of a Python script for the automatic generation of IIIF manifests. The tool includes a simplified interface, designed to allow non-programmers (e.g., the CSAC early-stage researchers) to create JSON structures directly from visual datasets. This reduced time and complexity while ensuring accuracy, standardisation, and reproducibility.

Pinpoint what has not been used and explain why

During the design and implementation phases, certain technologies and solutions were deliberately not adopted, with clear motivations:

- proprietary digital asset management platforms were avoided in favour of open-source infrastructures. This prevented potential vendor lock-in and ensured that the institution could maintain full autonomy over its digital archive.
- commercial photogrammetry and 3D modelling software was not employed, given its high licensing costs and limited flexibility. Instead, open-source tools such as Meshroom and Blender were prioritised, guaranteeing cost efficiency and greater adaptability.
- some advanced but resource-intensive features (e.g., AI-driven automatic cataloguing or cloud-based proprietary storage) were excluded at this stage, since they were not aligned with the project's immediate priorities of sustainability, replicability, and local control over data.

This strategy ensured that the software ecosystem remained accessible, replicable, and interoperable, in accordance with international standards (FAIR, IIIF) and the long-term vision of creating a sustainable phygital archive.

For what concerns T-VedO project, several innovative (prototypal) software packages have been devised, referring to steps 4-7 of Figure 2.1.1.

STEP 4 - AI Depthmap Retrieval

Selection of AI Models: AI architecture should be selected based on the complexity of the painted scene. By way of example, by leveraging Zero-cross methods (e.g. Depth

Anything v.2.0) it is possible to estimate, using AI-based algorithms, a depth map of the scene.

From a formal point of view the problem is stated as follows: let $I = (I_k, k = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ be a set of n images representing the alleged 3D shape S of a subject, object or scene would have if painted by an artist. Since this work explores the reconstruction of 3D models from painted scenes, in this specific case $n = 1$. 3D retrieval of the painted scene is the process of finding a predictor p that can infer a shape $\hat{S} = p(I)$ that is as close as possible to the "expected shape" S . This is a typical minimization problem where objective function (named Loss Function) to be minimized is given by:

$$\mathcal{L}(I) = d(p(I), S) \quad (1)$$

It should be noticed that in this particular case, the ground truth of the 3D, i.e. the shape S , is not available and therefore it is not possible to assess the performance of AI-based methods using accuracy metrics and other performance criteria.

Figure 2.1.2. Exemplificative 3D modelling of the artworks "The father with the dancer" by Franco Gentilini, 1931, CSAC Museum, Parma (Italy).

Many network topologies have been used to evaluate the predictor, mostly sharing a common basic architecture "comprising an image encoding which maps the original image into a vector x named latent variable, using a sequence of convolution blocks and pooling operators followed by fully connected layers of neurons. The data retrieved in output are then decoded into the desired 3D model by using either fully connected layers or a deconvolution network".

According to the considerations drafted above, two fundamental aspects have to be explored:

- Which are the most suitable CNN architectures, and which are their 3D representations;
- How to select the proper loss function \mathcal{L} .

We selected a representative set of zero-shot SOTA (State-Of-The-Art) models to evaluate their applicability to the generation of depth maps from paintings for tactile purposes. The investigated models, with their tested versions, include:

- Depth Anything (v1 and v2), based on dense prediction transformer architecture and known for strong generalization capabilities through large-scale training with labelled (synthetic) and unlabeled (real, via pseudo-labelling) data.
- Marigold Innovative approach based on diffusive models (Stable Diffusion), fine-tuned on synthetic data for affine-invariant depth estimation, promising fine detail generation.
- Metric3D (v2): transformer-based model (ViT - Vision Transformers trained on a large dataset (>16M images) for the estimation of metric depth and surface normal, with focus on zero-shot generalization and improved metric ambiguity handling.
- ZoeDepth: the model integrates a relative depth estimation approach, such as MiDaS, with domain-specific metric heads employing a metric bins module. This design aims to combine the generalization capabilities of relative depth estimation with the ability to predict depth in absolute physical units.
- UniDepth (v1, v2, v2_old): it proposes unified architecture (based on ViT or ConvNeXt) for universal metric depth estimation, introducing a self-prompting camera module and a pseudo-spherical representation. (Note: the v2 version differs significantly from v2_old in architecture and artefact handling).
- GeoWizard (v1 and v2): diffusion-based model (Stable Diffusion v1 for v1, v2 for v2) extended to jointly generate depths and normals, using a geometry switcher and a scene distribution decoupler to handle different layouts.
- Depth-Pro: recent multi-scale ViT-based model focused on the generation of high-resolution metric depth maps (native 1536x1536) with particularly accurate contours and fast inference times.

Due to their zero-shot nature, these models were applied directly to the digital images of the selected paintings, using publicly available implementations and pre-trained weights released by the authors, without any specific fine-tuning on the artistic domain. Basically, the experiment evaluates how these models, trained to infer three-dimensional geometry from real scenes, interpret a physically flat surface (the painting) representing a potentially three-dimensional scene through artistic conventions. The aim was not to optimize performance on these paintings, but to

evaluate the inherent ability of these models, trained on predominantly photographic and synthetic data, to extrapolate a plausible spatial structure by applying patterns learnt from the 3D world to a visually distinct input with no real physical depth. The evaluation then focuses on the quality of the out-of-the-box output and its suitability for the final purpose: the creation of meaningful haptic patterns. In essence, we test whether and how these tools interpret the two-dimensional representation of a three-dimensional world, almost "projecting" onto it the logic learnt from photographic input.

Models are trained using several datasets available in literature, despite these are not related to art paintings: BlendedMVS, Hypersim, IRS and TartanAir (see Figure 2.1.3).

Figure 2.1.3. Datasets used to train the AI-based Zero-Shot Methods.

Dealing with methods for the assessment of the AI-based reconstruction performance, there is a short list of methods for both quantitative and qualitative criteria. From the quantitative point of view, it should be noticed that one of the most relevant challenges in reconstructing 3D models starting from 2D images from an artwork is the unavailability of the ground truth since no 3D model exists for a painted scene. Therefore, the Loss functions adopted for training the CNN architectures are required to rely on a "simulated" ground truth which is a given model in the training dataset that resemble the subject of the painted scene. When using voxel grids as the output representation, the loss function is typically designed to compare the predicted and ground-truth voxel occupancy values.

When working with mesh representations three more Functions can be defined:

a) Surface Loss: measures the distance between corresponding vertices on the predicted and expected ground-truth meshes. It minimizes the distance between the surfaces of the two meshes.

b) Laplacian Regularization Loss: it penalizes large distortions or deformations in the predicted mesh by regularizing the local geometric structure. It is often used to encourage smooth surfaces.

c) Edge Length Loss: it penalizes unrealistic edge lengths in the predicted mesh, ensuring that the edges between vertices have consistent lengths, resulting in a smoother, more natural 3D shape.

From a qualitative viewpoint, we defined a number of Evaluation Criteria to assess the performance of AI-based depthmap retrieval:

- Fine details – Models trained on photos may over-smooth details in painted imagery
- Contour definition – clear edges are key for perception of the 3D model
- Spatial consistency – the depth should not produce “jumps” or discontinuities unless intended by the artist
- Artistic perspective management – artists use perspective intentionally, sometimes realistically (Renaissance) and sometimes distorted (Cubism, Surrealism)
- Absence of topological artifacts – depth maps should not introduce holes, floating regions, or inverted surfaces
- Suitability for tactile 3D printing – ensures that the model obtainable from the depthmap is usable for physical reproduction

STEP 5 – Retrieval of 2.5D and 3D Models

In this step we used the depth map or the retrieved mesh/point cloud/volumetric model as a guide to reconstruct the painted scene. Geometric modeling methods are needed to add volume and detail to objects/subjects. This can be achieved using a variety of approaches. Surface-reconstruction algorithms such as Poisson surface reconstruction or Delaunay triangulation convert sparse point clouds into watertight meshes, while multi-view stereo (MVS) and structure-from-motion (SfM) pipelines can refine geometry when multiple images are available.

Mesh-editing and sculpting tools—such as those provided by Blender, MeshLab, or Houdini—allow manual refinement and procedural enhancement of textures and micro-geometry. When the goal is to blend reconstructed geometry with segmentation results, frameworks like Segment Anything (SAM) or Mask R-CNN are used to isolate objects prior to volumetric modeling, ensuring that volume and detail are assigned to the correct regions. These combined classical and learning-based

methods yield robust 3D reconstructions with realistic depth, texture, and structural fidelity.

STEP 6 - Smoothing and Background adding

When combined with AI-assisted segmentation tools like Segment Anything (SAM), artists and technicians can selectively isolate regions for refinement before importing them into the CAD environment. This hybrid workflow—merging automated segmentation with manual CAD-based detailing—ensures both geometric precision and the creative flexibility required for faithful reconstruction.

STEP 7 - CAD Model Refining

This step encompasses:

- Saving the file in a compatible format (e.g., STL, OBJ, or PLY). Creating a Surface Model, using the mesh as a reference to generate NURBS (Non-Uniform Rational B-Splines) surfaces.
- Generating a Solid Model and convert the surface model into a solid CAD model. In this step it is important to ensure the model has no gaps or overlaps in geometry. Refining the CAD Model: add design features like fillets, holes, or patterns as needed and optimize the geometry for specific applications. This task should be accomplished using CAD software packages. Exporting the CAD Model: save the file in the desired CAD format (e.g., STEP, IGES, or DXF). This ensures the availability of a 3D model.

Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

Training on use and maintenance

The introduction of the Visionaria technologies to museum staff and stakeholders was carefully structured in order to ensure both operational autonomy and long-term sustainability of the system. A multi-layered training and familiarisation plan was implemented, with the following components:

- Training on use and maintenance. Dedicated workshops were organised to train the CSAC staff, early-stage researchers, and technical collaborators on the daily use and maintenance of the digital infrastructure. These included:
- procedures for uploading and publishing new works on the IIF-based platform;
- management of metadata in line with ICCD and international standards;

- technical routines for system backup, file conversion, and interoperability checks;
- maintenance of hardware devices (scanner, 3D printers, VR headsets, and interactive totems).

T-VedO project is structured for the introduction of a range of 3D replicas of 2D artworks located in CSAC to be enjoyed by blind people. Tactile reproductions will be located near the original artwork if this is exposed to the public. Otherwise they will be available in the museum. All tactile models will be accompanied by a verbal description of both the author and the artwork. Two different descriptions will be available in the website, as described in Annex 2 of this report.

Describe opportunities and objectives

The primary objective of Visionaria Project was to guarantee full independence of the CSAC in managing its phygital archive without reliance on external providers. Training also opened new opportunities for staff and early-stage researchers by providing advanced digital skills (IIIF, photogrammetry, 3D modelling, virtual tour management), which can be applied to other projects, research activities, and collaborations. The project has therefore strengthened the role of the CSAC as a centre of competence and innovation for cultural heritage valorisation.

Dealing with T-VedO project, all experimentation took place at University of Florence since CSAC was closed and not operative. A number of artworks were selected and treated using both the innovative algorithms and the linguistic and art historical-based approach, as deeply described below.

Familiarise staff with technology through training sessions and workshops on self-guided learning

Staff members and grant recipients participated in hands-on training sessions, where they learned by directly working with the technologies (scanner, 3D workflows, VR navigation, IIIF manifest creation). In addition, self-guided learning resources were created: a shared repository containing manuals, tutorials, templates, and technical documentation. This combination of guided and autonomous learning ensured flexibility and the consolidation of competences.

Collect staff feedback

Continuous feedback was collected throughout the implementation phase, both informally during training sessions and formally through evaluation meetings. Staff highlighted the value of having simplified interfaces (e.g., the Python tool for automated IIIF manifest generation) and stressed the importance of maintaining documentation for future staff turnover. Feedback was integrated into the refinement of workflows, ensuring that the technologies introduced were not only effective but also user-friendly and aligned with daily practices at the CSAC.

Describe the experimentation session

Evaluate with real users to track of the effectiveness and appropriateness of the proposed solutions

Dealing with Visionaria Project, as soon as the CSAC reopens, the staff will test, through tools such as questionnaires, the effectiveness and appropriateness of the proposed solutions with real and virtual visitors.

Dealing with T-VedO Project, for the creation of the textual mediation materials for the works included in the PNRR itinerary, a systematic study of the cultural heritage preserved at the CSAC was first undertaken. The initial step was to define a selection of works on which to plan the interventions envisaged in the subsequent phases.

This selection was based on a series of agreed criteria:

- a) the historical and artistic significance of each work and its emblematic nature in relation to CSAC's collecting policies;
- b) the representativeness of the richness and variety of CSAC's collections (around 12 million pieces across five sections – art, photography, media, fashion, design);
- c) their location within CSAC's exhibition spaces or archive;
- d) their state of conservation and the feasibility of moving them;
- e) the practical applicability of further technological developments aimed at enhanced enjoyment of the works.

In this respect, several on-site inspections of the museum and archive spaces were also crucial, allowing the team to design a hypothesis for an "augmented" exhibition itinerary through the interventions planned by the project.

The result of this selection process led to the identification of eight case-study works:

1. La giovinezza (Uomo a cavallo) (1936) by Mario Sironi;
2. Grande grigio bruno (1954) by Carla Accardi;
3. Superficie a tessitura vibratile (1961) by Getulio Alviani;
4. Il Fiocinatore (o Il Pescatore) (1933–34) by Lucio Fontana;
5. Early Dynastic (1971) by Giulio Paolini;
6. Lo spirato (1968–73) by Luciano Fabro;
7. Pescatore di Camogli (undated [1950–60]) by Bruno Stefani;

8. Il divorzio è un tuo diritto, difendilo, vota no (undated [1974]) by Ettore Vitale.

Moreover the procedure was tested to other two case studies: Aldo Bergonzoni – Mia Madre and Franco Gentilini – Il Padre e la Ballerina. For these two cases only 3D digital reconstruction was carried out.

The drafting of the related historical-artistic dissemination sheets required a multi-faceted research approach, based on a combination of archival investigation, stylistic analysis, and comparison with the most up-to-date critical bibliography. The work began with a thorough survey of the documentary materials available at CSAC, including both primary sources (inventory cards, catalogues, photographic documentation) and archival references related to the provenance of the works. This preliminary information formed the basis for defining the historical and collecting context of each piece.

In some cases, the identification of gaps or discrepancies necessitated cross-checking with photographic documentation and catalogues from past exhibitions. At the same time, a direct analysis of the works was carried out, whenever possible, in order to identify stylistic, technical (supports, materials, any restorations), and iconographic elements not always discernible from secondary documentation alone. A further step involved consulting critical literature, with particular attention to the most recent studies and monographs dedicated to the artists concerned. The comparison of these various sources made it possible to contextualize the works not only from a stylistic and chronological perspective, but also in relation to the cultural and historical dynamics of the period and, more broadly, within the artistic trajectories of twentieth-century Italy and the collecting history of CSAC. The information thus gathered was synthesized and organized into sheets aimed at a specialist audience, seeking to combine scientific rigor with clarity of presentation. Each sheet followed uniform criteria, including identifying data of the work (author, title, date, technique, location), description and formal analysis, historical and cultural contextualization, and reference bibliography.

In this way, the research work is aimed not only to document the works, but also to make them accessible to a specialist audience and, through subsequent linguistic adaptations, to a wide variety of different publics. We present a set of case studies we developed during the project. To synthesize the Report, we include the 3D reconstruction and the 3D printing entirely only the first case study, so as to fully understand the whole methodology.

Identify strengths and weaknesses (possibly using a SWOT analysis)

One of the strengths of the project lies in the collaboration between the University of Parma (pertaining to the entities located in the Northern Italy Regions) and the company Basilink Art (located in the Southern Regions), which intends to propose

itself as a model of technological development in the cultural sphere of the country, creating a synergy not only between entities of different nature, but also between realities operating in different economic-territorial contexts. The increase of Industrial Research and Experimental Development processes is pursued thanks to the cohesion between academic research and IT creation, stimulating innovative production processes supported by recognized scholars and researchers; simultaneously implementing training processes (with the issuance of 5 research grants, aimed at young three-year and master's degree graduates and new graduate students) inherent to the use of new technologies and the enhancement of heritage in the museological and historical-artistic sphere.

Weaknesses already include a discrepancy between the timing of private enterprise and that of public administration, generated by a series of delays in procurement of supplies and instrumentation, contracting of services, and administrative time for recruitment of early-stage researchers. Furthermore, following a disastrous event that struck the CSAC in October 2024, it was closed down, as the safety and accessibility conditions were not sufficient to guarantee the protection and comfort of staff, visitors and scholars. This extraordinary situation significantly slowed down the work of the early-stage researchers and the company. Despite the difficulties, both groups still managed to complete their assigned tasks on schedule.

Recent studies suggest that the mere tactile exploration of 3D models (even in case these are optimally reproducing the original painting) is not sufficient to fully understand, and enjoy, the artwork. Blind people understanding of the original artwork is, in fact, subject to a lot of factors (e.g., sensitivity and personal ability of the person, size and quality of the tactile model); for this reason a good quality verbal guidance is essential in order to appreciate even the best possible artistic relief reproduction of a given painting. Such a verbal description is usually provided by a sighted person (museum employee, accompanying person, etc.); this allows the blind person to build a complete mental image of the tactile model, and to not be stopped by the lack of comprehension of a single element of the bas-relief. The presence of another person, however, could be perceived as a limiting factor in enjoying the artwork since the blind person is forced to discover in the perspective of someone else; art is through a language that requires autonomy and freedom to be fully apprehended.

The introduction of an automatic verbal guide could increase the autonomy of the user during the exploration, allowing him to lead the experience (e.g., autonomously establishing the time needed for a full appreciation, moving the hands freely, taking time to think, etc.), achieving the same freedom of sighted people. To fulfil this goal, the guide should not be merely automatic (e.g., audio-guide such as the ones already available for sighted people), but rather "active" i.e., capable of following the user's movements so as to provide information in form of verbal descriptions.

This ambitious objective is still far to be accomplished in scientific literature, not only for technical reasons: guiding a BP in the exploration of an artwork cannot be limited to a description of an artwork scene and/or of touched areas, but is rather a gradual help to acquire information and to organize it into a "mental scheme" that become progressively more and more complete and detailed. However, the design of a first-attempt system able to automatically provide verbal information of touched areas is still an advancement of the state of the art in this topic.

Explain how the proposed solutions can foster citizens participation, accessibility, and social inclusion

The University of Parma deals with the structuring of new museum paths, real and virtual, thanks to the use of tactile and digital materials made by the partner company. It is intended to constitute a tactile museum route with the use of 3D printed models, suitable for use by the visually impaired public. Such a path may allow a new approach to the museum collection also by younger audiences so as to increase the mediation activities provided by the CSAC, encouraging accessibility and interactivity of the heritage. A digital museum tour usable through special VR access hardware was also be created.

Conclusions

Identify technological gaps

During the project implementation, some technological gaps emerged that will require further development in future phases:

- server-side infrastructure: at the current stage, the CSAC does not yet have a fully internal server infrastructure to independently host the IIIF environment. Servers are temporarily managed by the project's technical partners, and a future migration plan is necessary to guarantee complete institutional autonomy;
- accessibility tools: while tactile 3D reproductions have been created for visually impaired audiences, additional accessibility features such as Braille labels, haptic interfaces, and audio descriptions are not yet integrated and remain a priority for future development.

Describe any unforeseen issues that arose during the implementation

Several unforeseen issues were encountered during the implementation phase:

- administrative delays: public procurement and recruitment procedures were slower than expected, causing delays in the delivery of equipment (e.g., scanner, 3D hardware) and in the activation of research grants;

- timing mismatch between public and private partners: different operating speeds and procedures between university administration and private companies created challenges in coordinating the workflow.

Delineate further lines of research

Visionaria is at the intersection between the physical and digital worlds, with the aim of overcoming the structural limitations of traditional use of cultural and archival heritage. The main intent was not only to equip the Centre with innovative tools, but above all to enable a profound and lasting cultural and organisational transformation, restoring autonomy and operational capacity. Visionaria is now a digital platform that has broadened the public's perception, built new paths to knowledge, and strengthened the CSAC as an autonomous, innovative institution with a promising future. Its strength lies not only in numbers – 20 works digitised in 3D, 10 printed, dozens of works scanned in 2D, a complete virtual tour, an interoperable archive – but in its strategic and systemic approach, which restores value to heritage, skills to people and tools to the territory.

Visionaria has made the archive public, inclusive and global, concretely implementing the principles of the National Digital Library and meeting international standards of accessibility, interoperability and digital preservation of cultural heritage promoted by institutions such as UNESCO, Europeana, ICOM and ICCROM. To make all this possible, the project involved targeted investment in new technologies – including planetary scanners, graphics workstations, 3D modelling and rendering software, VR headsets and touch systems – as well as the employment of skilled human resources, such as developers, digital curators, 3D artists, trainers and specialised technicians. These resources were fundamental in creating not only a final product, but also a stable operational and cultural structure that can be managed and expanded by the CSAC in complete autonomy in the coming years.

Referring to T-VedO Project, future works will be addressed to several technical aspects. From a technical point of view, ReViP Laboratory at University of Florence presented a brief feasibility study of a system to improve blind people tactile exploration of bas-reliefs, where a possible methodology for conceiving an active guide for BP was sketched.

Such a designed system consists of:

1. A physical bas-relief to be explored by BP and its digital counterpart (e.g., a high-definition point cloud/polygonal model describing it). Even if, in principle, any kind of bas-relief could be used for developing the BES, where shape from shading-based methods is devised to obtain both 3D polygonal models (e.g., STL) and a physical prototype of such a digital model starting from a shaded picture (for example a renaissance painting). In fact, by using such a procedure both the

physical and digital 3D information are directly available. In any case, the proposed procedure can be applied to any kind of bas-relief (or in case the bas-relief is not allowed to be touched, to a replica) since the required initial information (polygonal model) can be easily achieved using a commercial 3D scanner.

2. A 3D acquisition device capable of (i) tracking the user hands and (ii) detecting the position of the physical bas-relief in its reference frame. The device used to build the system is the Microsoft Kinect®. As widely known, it consists of a projector-camera triangulation device furnished with a 43° vertical by 57° horizontal field of view that covers, at 1 m distance a visible rectangle of 0.8 m x 1.1 m. Such a field of view, to be considered as a plausible value for tracking, is required to cover the typical dimension of tactile bas-reliefs.
3. A PC workstation, in control of the whole BES. This element is responsible for the hand tracking, the required calculations (point clouds registration and distances computation, as previously described) and for the touch identification. The hardware needs to be equipped for GPU computing, and with hand tracking performances comparable with, to assure satisfying results.
4. An Audio system (this task is not currently implemented). Since the final outcome of the BES is, as already mentioned above, a verbal description of the scene and/or of touched objects or features, the system is equipped with headsets/headphones. Of course, to locate headsets could be difficult for unaccompanied BP; unfortunately, since the installation is specifically addressed to museum installations, the use of audio speakers could not represent a valid option.

2.2. MUSAD: A scalable and flexible digital platform for the valorisation of "widespread museums". The case of the museum system of the Istituto Suor Orsola Benincasa charity

Outline clear goals and objectives

The MUSAD project (Musealità Scalabile e Diffusa) responds to the call for proposals of Spoke 4 - Virtual Technologies for Museums and Art Collections under the extended PNRR partnership number 5 - CHANGES: Cultural Heritage Innovation for Next-Gen Sustainable Society, addressing theme number 6, "A scalable and flexible digital platform for the enhancement of 'widespread museality': The case of the museum system of the Ente Morale Istituto Suor Orsola Benincasa (SMA UNISOB)". The

SMA UNISOB core case serves as a playground to build a pioneering prototype for an interactive virtual gallery, aiming to advance the concept of "widespread museality" by utilizing innovative technologies to digitize and exhibit the extensive art collections of the Suor Orsola Benincasa Institute, representing an exemplary of Type C – widespread art gallery. This initiative addresses the challenges faced by peripheral cultural institutions, such as limited accessibility and resources, by offering scalable and flexible solutions to enhance digital engagement with cultural heritage.

At its core, the project consists of two main components: the DROSOS digital library, and the MNEMOS platform. DROSOS is designed to catalog and preserve a curated selection of the institute's vast collection, which includes over 24,000 prints, 1,000 drawings, watercolors by Giacinto Gigante, 450 paintings, and a variety of 3D artifacts such as vases and statues. To showcase the system's capabilities, the MUSAD project will digitize 100 representative artworks spanning multiple media, including prints, drawings, paintings, and sculptures, all captured to high-resolution standards. This repository will ensure the long-term preservation of these works and provide non-technical users with a web-based, user-friendly interface to access them, with the aim of enabling the enrichment of the digitalized stored collection in subsequent digitalization efforts. The MNEMOS platform functions as an immersive virtual environment and a digital twin of the institute's exhibition spaces, enabling curators to design, configure, and present virtual exhibitions without programming skills. Seamlessly integrated with DROSOS, MNEMOS allows the direct importation of digitized works into an interactive 3D environment. The platform includes modular design elements, such as customizable exhibition furniture, and interactive multimedia features, including audio guides and embedded videos. These virtual exhibitions aim to replicate the fluidity and autonomy of exploring a physical gallery while offering enhanced digital functionalities. The integration of DROSOS and MNEMOS facilitates a seamless workflow from digitization to virtual exhibition, empowering institutions to enrich their cultural offerings and engage a broader audience.

The project also incorporates advanced digitalization activities, such as laser scanning and 3D reconstruction of exhibition spaces to produce Building Information Models (BIM) at LOD 300 level, ensuring accurate and detailed digital representations of museum environments. These models are incorporated into the MNEMOS platform, allowing the creation of highly realistic and engaging virtual exhibits also for the permanent exhibition spaces.

One of the project's most innovative features is the development of KYBER, a generative AI-based assistant designed to assist curators in creating virtual exhibits and defining exhibition paths in 3D spaces. KYBER leverages a low-environmental-impact Large Language Model (LLM) to provide multimodal, bilingual (Italian-English) insights and suggestions. Its design emphasizes flexibility and adaptability, enabling

curators to simplify exhibit planning and personalize cultural narratives. KYBER's integration with MNEMOS and DROSOS streamlines workflows, ensuring curators can efficiently manage and enhance virtual exhibition experiences.

The SMA UNISOB core case, with its integrated approach to digitization, virtual exhibition, and AI-enhanced curation, sets a benchmark for innovation in digital cultural heritage, promoting accessibility, sustainability, and inclusivity for institutions of all sizes, as the central goal of the core case is to establish a methodological and technological framework that can be adapted by other institutions, particularly those in remote or underserved areas, addressing the specific needs of small museums and cultural institutions, which often struggle to adopt advanced technologies due to budgetary and infrastructural constraints. As part of the larger Spoke 4 initiative, the core case also represents a model for the future of digital museology, blending heritage preservation with cutting-edge digital tools to redefine the visitor experience.

Describe knowledge sharing among project participants

The knowledge exchange process among the project participants—UNISOB (as the cultural heritage partner), Tecno.Art, UNIOR, and GLOSSA SRL (the cascade call awardees)—has been structured to foster effective communication, goal alignment, and mutual collaboration throughout the project's implementation. Central to this effort were the regular plenary meetings organized by UNISOB, with seven sessions held between October 8, 2024, and January 8, 2025.

These meetings played a pivotal role in aligning the partners on the operational objectives and methodological framework defined by Spoke 4, which were introduced and explained by UNISOB to the winning partners. The plenary sessions also created an opportunity for Tecno.Art and GLOSSA to share insights into the methodologies and technologies used for digitization, such as laser scanning and 3D modeling, while discussing their implications and potential applications. Regular updates on the progress of Tecno.Art's digital acquisition of UNISOB's museum spaces were communicated both during site visits and in these plenary sessions, ensuring a transparent and cooperative workflow among all partners. UNISOB also leveraged the meetings to provide contextual information about the broader research objectives of Spoke 4.

During the plenary calls, UNISOB highlighted the unique aspects of its case study, including updates on the outcomes of the MOSTRE VIRTUALI project, which served as a precursor to the work undertaken within Spoke 4. Based on this groundwork, UNISOB articulated its expectations for the DROSOS platform as the digital archive for its art collections and for the MNEMOS platform as its virtual museum. Specific requirements

for the virtual representation of museum spaces were presented, emphasizing the need for modular and scalable solutions to support a variety of digital exhibitions, in line with the institution's Exhibition Plan. For its university museums, UNISOB requested high-resolution 3D models that allow seamless navigation and detailed interaction with permanent exhibitions.

To support the partners' work, UNISOB provided essential resources, including detailed floor plans of the spaces to be digitized, a comprehensive list of objects for digitization, and accompanying photographic and textual documentation. In return, GLOSSA shared examples of relevant projects developed for institutions like the National Archaeological Museum of Naples, Palazzo Corsini, and the Accademia Nazionale dei Lincei, while incorporating UNISOB's feedback to tailor the DROSOS platform to its specific needs. The partners also reached an agreement to adopt ATON as the basis for the MNEMOS platform, in alignment with UNISOB's request.

Additionally, Tecno.Art and GLOSSA facilitated knowledge sharing by providing demonstrations and technical deliverables as outlined in the project. These included D1.1, which documented the topographical mapping, point cloud survey, and photographic survey of the Garden and Corridor of the Claustro, the Exhibition Floor, the Historical Museum, and the Pagliara Museum; and D2.1, which featured 3D reconstructions of selected rooms and exhibits from the Pagliara Museum. These contributions ensured that the platforms and tools developed were closely aligned with the project's goals and UNISOB's expectations.

To further illustrate the exchange of knowledge regarding the technologies employed, Tecno.Art not only showcased its advanced tools and methodologies for 3D space acquisition but also actively engaged with UNISOB by involving UNISOB staff (researchers and PhD students) in the acquisition phases, providing hands-on exposure and foundational training in cultural heritage three-dimensional digitization techniques. For the digitization of the areas within UNISOB, the company Tecno.Art employed advanced tools for surveying both indoor and outdoor spaces. In particular, SLAM (Fig. 2.2.1) (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping) technology was used, combining LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) sensors and IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) cameras to create 3D maps and localize positions in real time (Fig. 2.2.2). Additionally, three-dimensional space acquisition technologies were adopted through photogrammetry, supported by aerial drones (Fig. 2.2.3). The processes implemented by Tecno.Art were strongly inspired by the guidelines shared by UNISOB, derived from the document "A reproducible workflow for the creation of digital twins in the cultural heritage domain". Tecno.Art's operators enthusiastically welcomed the participation of the UNISOB staff, actively involved in the acquisition phases.

Figure 2.2.1. Tecno.Art' operator begins the scanning path on the area wearing the Navvis VLX device (SLAM).

Figure 2.2.2. Digital map, on a Navvis VLX (SLAM) device, generated after an initial acquisition of the UNISOB exhibition area.

Figure 2.2.3. Architecture acquisition with drone in the Museum Center Gallery

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

For the first phase of digitisation of the UNISOB environments, the so-called acquisition phase, survey operations were carried out following the procedures explained in the Spoke 4 Guidelines, in paragraph "3.2.1" regarding STEP1 (Acquisition phase). The Tecno.Art company began the acquisition phase by carrying out an inspection of the areas of design interest, taking into account the checklist of the optimal parameters of the environment, the architectural spaces, lights, furnishings, and artifacts present. After that, the instruments useful for the survey were chosen based on the type of environments. Instruments suitable for internal and external surveys were used. The first operational phase, as per guidelines, involved the extraction of dense point clouds through SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping) survey with portable instruments, including the 3D scan NavVis VLX2 (Fig. 2.2.4), LEICA BLK2GO (Fig. 2.2.5), and aerial photogrammetry for internal environments. For external environments, long-range instruments such as the LEICA TS16 (Fig. 2.2.6), LEICA RTC360-SLAM (Fig. 2.2.7), and aerial photogrammetry via drone (Fig. 2.2.8) were used to extract RAW files and previews of the RAWp files, which will then be processed and stored for possible future re-elaboration.

Figure 2.2.4. Tecno.Art' operator begins the scanning path on the area wearing the Navvis VLX dev. (SLAM).

Figure 2.2.5. Tecno.Art' operator begins the scanning path with the portable LAICA BLK2GO

Figure 2.2.6. LAICA TS16 station located centrally in the Cloister Garden at the University

Figure 2.2.7. LAICA RTV360 scanner during one of the sessions in the Cloister Garden and the results.

The digital acquisitions carried out within the MUSAD project include both architectural surveys and three-dimensional models of artworks and spaces. A complete environmental survey of the Cloister was delivered in DWG format, complemented by four separate PDF files corresponding to the ground floor, first floor, second floor, and third floor. Together, these materials amount to approximately 1.6 MB.

In terms of artworks, nineteen 3D models were created and exported in OBJ and GLB/GLTF formats to ensure full compatibility with the MNEMOS system (Fig. 2.2.8). The total size of these models is about 22 GB. These models not only reproduce the objects with a high degree of fidelity but also allow their integration into interactive exhibition scenarios.

Figure 2.2.8. Examples of examples of digitized wooden sculptures.

Regarding architectural spaces, a comprehensive 3D model of the entire Suor Orsola Benincasa complex was developed. This model was delivered in GLB, FBX, IFC, and RVT formats, with a total size of roughly 1 GB. The model provides both a global overview of the building and detailed renderings of specific areas, such as the corridors that are being repurposed as exhibition environments (Fig. 2.2.9, 2.2.10).

Figure 2.2.9. Overview of the entire Suor Orsola Benincasa complex.

Figure 2.2.10. Detail of the corridor used as an exhibition space.

All datasets, including plans and models, were generated and structured in compliance with the methodological guidelines set out by Spoke 4. Architectural drawings such as plans, elevations, and sections were directly extracted from the BIM model, following the project specifications. The models were created at a Level of

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Development (LOD) 300, ensuring a consistent balance between detail and manageability. For the 3D modeling of objects, a combined survey approach was employed, using either laser scanning or structured-light scanning together with photogrammetry. The resulting point cloud from the laser scanner survey was matched with photographic data, which were calibrated in the post-processing phase to enrich the 3D survey with chromatic information (RGB values). This optimized point cloud, refined by reducing noise and redundancy, was then used to generate a textured 3D mesh, which was subsequently exported into formats suitable for web use.

Features of the MUSAD platform

DROSOS offers a comprehensive set of functions for managing digital heritage data. Authorized users can create new records of different types, such as inventory cards, multimedia resources (including images, audio, video, and 3D models), or catalog entries, all based on ICCD cataloguing standards. Once created, these records can be edited through a dynamic interface that adapts to the type of card being handled. The interface allows users to update entered data, select terms from controlled vocabularies, apply formal validation checks, and even delete specific data fields without removing the entire record. Another key feature of DROSOS is the possibility of linking multimedia documents to descriptive records through a dedicated "data association" function (Fig. 2.2.11). Multimedia files can also be imported in bulk, enabling the integration of large sets of digital resources into the system. Finally, DROSOS provides tools for the metadata enrichment of all types of resources stored in the digital library, ensuring their consistent description and interoperability.

IDENTIFICAZIONE	
Tipo modulo	INVD
Codice modulo	1957

LOCALIZZAZIONE GEOGRAFICA AMMINISTRATIVA	
<i>LOCALIZZAZIONE</i>	
Regione	Campania
Provincia	NA
Comune	Napoli
<i>COLLOCAZIONE SPECIFICA</i>	
Denominazione contenitore fisico	Museo Pagliara
Indicazioni viabilistiche	Via Suor Orsola, 10 - 80135
Specifiche	Gabinetto Stampe - Cartella 52 bis

OGGETTO DELL'INVENTARIAZIONE	
Oggetto	Disegno
Titolo	Due giocatori di carte
Epoca	sec. XIX
Iscrizioni	recto: De Nardis; Tirituppete e stette/ contente/ non te pigliare malumori; De Nardis

AUTORE/AMBITO	
Autore	
Autore	Anonimo

Figure 2.2.11. DROSOS interface showing the 'Data Association' function, which allows linking a digital resource to a descriptive record.

MNEMOS extends these archival functions into the domain of virtual exhibitions. The process of creating a virtual exhibition begins in DROSOS (Fig. 2.2.12), where the curator defines metadata and selects the exhibition environment. Curators can upload 3D models of rooms or link panoramic photographs, which then become part of the virtual setup. Once the environment has been created, an interactive editing mode allows curators to navigate and customize the space directly in their web browser. Within this mode, the AI-based module KYBER can be activated to suggest artworks that best fit the chosen theme, presenting them in a selectable list (Fig. 2.2.13). The selected objects, particularly those with associated 3D models, can then be placed in the exhibition space, where they may be freely moved, rotated, or removed. MNEMOS also supports further personalization by enabling the enrichment of the environment with additional multimedia elements, such as panoramic images, to create more immersive experiences.

Figure 2.2.12. Creation of an exhibition in DROSOS.

Figure 2.2.13. MNEMOS user interface for creating a virtual exhibition, showing the list of 3D models suggested by KYBER and the list of panoramic photos associated with the exhibition environment.

KYBER plays a pivotal role in supporting curators with AI-driven exhibition design. The system can generate exhibition proposals starting from multimodal prompts provided by the curator, combining three advanced modes of retrieval: natural language

queries, image-based searches, and hybrid combinations of text and images. This flexibility allows curators to guide the creation of thematically and aesthetically coherent exhibitions with minimal effort. KYBER queries the DROSOS database to identify artworks relevant to the requested theme, material, technique, date, or author, and can also expand the search to external databases, offering a broader scope of exploration. Once suitable works are retrieved, KYBER provides textual narratives that explain curatorial choices, highlight connections among selected items, and suggest possible exhibition arrangements. Several use cases demonstrate the versatility of KYBER. For example, a curator preparing a show on the themes of wealth and poverty in the 19th century may rely on KYBER to identify relevant costume designs within DROSOS and receive a curatorial narrative linking them together. In another case, when designing a battle-themed exhibition inspired by a well-known painting, the curator can upload the image to KYBER and obtain similar works from the archive. Finally, when focusing on the artistic use of marble, KYBER can compile a selection of sculptures from both DROSOS and external repositories, offering a basis for a comparative exhibition that showcases different artistic interpretations of the material.

Implementation details

For the development of DROSOS, several open-source technologies were adopted. The application server Apache Tomcat is used to run and manage the backend application, while Apache Lucene provides indexing and efficient search capabilities through its API. The entire system is built on Java 18, which supports integration with Tomcat and Keycloak. PostgreSQL is employed as the relational database management system to store and handle the catalogue information. Finally, user management, authentication, and authorization are ensured through Keycloak, an open-source identity and access management solution. All components are open-source, guaranteeing transparency and sustainability.

The software stack for MNEMOS also relies entirely on open-source technologies. Its foundation is ATON, a framework developed by CNR for the generation and delivery of virtual exhibitions. The user interface and interaction logic are built with standard web technologies (HTML, CSS, and JavaScript) while server-side functionalities are managed through Node.js. Three.js, a widely used library for 3D graphics, enables rendering and navigation in virtual environments, with digital objects integrated using the open-standard glTF format. MNEMOS is also connected to DROSOS through dedicated APIs, which allow the import and management of catalogued items within the exhibitions.

For KYBER, a suite of advanced AI-oriented open-source libraries and frameworks has been implemented. Hugging Face libraries support the generation of vector embeddings from textual metadata, enabling efficient retrieval of artworks based on

semantic similarity, as well as cross-modal searches combining text and images. Sentence Transformers are used to produce dense semantic representations of descriptive texts, further strengthening multimodal retrieval capabilities. The system also integrates llama-cpp, an open-source framework for running large language models efficiently on a wide range of hardware, without requiring costly GPU-based infrastructures. On top of this, llama-cpp-agent extends llama-cpp by implementing the AI agent logic, orchestrating retrieval and generation processes to support the digital curator in creating coherent and meaningful exhibition pathways. Regarding the AI assistant specifically, different language models with fewer than nine billion parameters were tested. The model currently adopted is Gemma 4B, chosen as the best compromise between model size, runtime performance, ability to follow instructions, and the presence of built-in safeguard mechanisms. Its multimodal capabilities make it particularly well-suited for the needs of this project. For fine-tuning, only public-domain datasets were employed, including a mix of reliable and domain-relevant sources such as Europeana, WikiArt, and several datasets available on Hugging Face. The criteria guiding dataset selection included salience with respect to the assistant's application domain, diversity of content, and the intrinsic quality of the data, with special consideration given to the reputation of the sources, such as Europeana, whose data are openly licensed. Both the size and the quality of the selected datasets have been deemed sufficient to support an effective post-tuning process, yielding satisfactory results in the project's experimental context.

The reliance on open-source technologies and publicly available datasets ensures transparency, adaptability, and cost-effective scalability, while also reinforcing the cultural and ethical sustainability of the KYBER component.

Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

A half-day training workshop will be organized during the first two weeks of October 2025. The workshop will be addressed to curators and other target stakeholders and is designed to familiarize participants with the MUSAD platform while collecting structured user feedback.

The workshop is expected to involve between six and eight participants and will include an introduction to the project, a guided demonstration of the main modules of the platform (DROSOS, MNEMOS, and the AI-based assistant), and a hands-on exercise where participants will experiment with data entry, metadata enrichment, and exhibition creation. After completing these activities, participants will experience the exhibitions they created as visitors, allowing them to reflect on both the creation and the consumption processes.

Feedback will be collected through multiple channels, including short questionnaires on user experience, perceived usability, and satisfaction, both as digital curators and digital exhibition visitors, as well as structured comments on the clarity of workflows and the overall effectiveness of the platform. To complement this, a SWOT analysis will be conducted, enabling participants to reflect on the strengths and weaknesses of the system, as well as on opportunities and potential threats related to its long-term adoption. This approach will provide both immediate impressions of the platform's usability and more strategic insights into its perceived value, helping the development team refine future iterations of MUSAD.

Describe the experimentation session

The user evaluations are scheduled for October, following the final refinements of the platform. These sessions will serve to validate the effectiveness and appropriateness of MUSAD after its latest development cycle.

During the planned experimentation session with target users, represented by university students at first, participants will be invited to explore the MUSAD platform as visitors. After a short introduction and demonstration, they will be given time to navigate autonomously through exhibitions created within the system. The exploration will be semi-structured: participants will be encouraged to read introductory descriptions, examine captions, zoom into images, and interact with three-dimensional artefacts such as rotating or enlarging objects. They will also be asked to identify highlights of the exhibition and to select works that they consider particularly meaningful or engaging. The purpose of this activity will be to expose participants to the key informational and interactive features of MUSAD from a visitor's perspective and to collect feedback on usability, content clarity, and overall satisfaction with the experience.

At the end of the session, participants will complete an online questionnaire combining several established user experience assessment instruments. The questionnaire will include the Net Promoter Score to measure willingness to recommend the experience, the User Experience Questionnaire – Short to capture both hedonic and pragmatic aspects of interaction, the System Usability Scale to evaluate the usability of the virtual gallery environment, and the NASA Task Load Index to assess perceived workload during the interaction. In addition to these standardized tools, open-ended questions will invite participants to share reflections on strengths, limitations, and possible improvements to the platform.

This session will also allow a direct comparison with the baseline results collected with NAVIGA, the foundational prototype of the research work, highlighting improvements achieved with MUSAD as well as areas where further refinements may be needed.

Conclusions

From a technological perspective, the project introduced several innovative solutions across its three main components. In DROSOS, innovation lay primarily in its interoperability with MNEMOS and KYBER, the implementation of automated metadata generation for artworks, and the integration of Apache Lucene APIs to enable semantic search. The most significant challenges encountered in this module were related to managing very large, high-resolution files of digitized works and optimizing search queries across extensive datasets.

In MNEMOS, innovation was achieved through the integration of 3D rendering technologies within ATON, the possibility of designing and publishing virtual exhibitions without the need for coding skills, and the introduction of full 360-degree navigation within virtual museum environments. The main challenges here involved ensuring smooth browser-based rendering of complex 3D scenes, maintaining an intuitive user experience for curators, and guaranteeing seamless interoperability with the digital assets stored in DROSOS.

KYBER represented the most advanced technological innovation in the project. Its multimodal intelligence combines natural language understanding and visual analysis within a single curatorial workflow, opening new opportunities for the valorization of cultural heritage. The system also relies on a modular AI-agent architecture capable of orchestrating retrieval and generative processes, and it has been designed to democratize access to advanced AI technologies by exclusively adopting open-source solutions optimized for commodity hardware. Moreover, the project adapted Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) techniques specifically to the cultural heritage domain, developing embeddings tailored to artistic metadata. The difficulties encountered in this case concerned the variable quality of the metadata in DROSOS, the delicate balance between accurate retrieval and creative generation of exhibition pathways, and the technical complexity of synchronizing textual and visual representations in a coherent manner.

The project also highlighted several technical limits and open issues. For DROSOS, the main limitations included the management of very large attachments, the need for constant updates of the underlying infrastructure (Tomcat, PostgreSQL, and Keycloak), and the complexity of normalizing metadata imported from heterogeneous sources. In addition, the optimization of APIs was identified as essential to guarantee fast response times when queried by MNEMOS. For MNEMOS, the main limitations were linked to the handling of heavy 3D models, which may slow down the user experience, and the dependency of rendering quality on the client's graphical capabilities. The project also highlighted the need to further simplify editing interfaces for non-technical curators and to ensure consistent performance across different

browsers and devices. In KYBER, the identified limitations stemmed from its reliance on the completeness and accuracy of input metadata, the computational resources required by more complex models, and the difficulty of capturing subtle interpretative or cultural connections that remain the prerogative of human curators. Another challenge concerned the validation of automatically generated narratives, which still requires specific metrics to assess the coherence and curatorial quality of the results.

Overall, the integration of DROSOS, MNEMOS, and KYBER has demonstrated the feasibility of combining archival systems, immersive environments, and AI-driven curatorial support into a unified platform. At the same time, the lessons learned point to the need for continued refinement in data quality management, performance optimization, and user-centered design, in order to further strengthen the platform's role as a sustainable and innovative reference model for digital curation.

3. Research case studies

3.1. 3D Technologies for early-modern sculpture and digital strategies for museums. Terracotta sculptures by Antonio Begarelli in the Galleria Estense, Modena

Outline clear goals and objectives

Describe the initial situation

The Galleria Estense in Modena is part of the Gallerie Estensi (Direzione Regionale Musei Emilia-Romagna), a national museum complex that also includes the Biblioteca Estense Universitaria (Modena), the Museo Lapidario (Modena), the Palazzo Ducale (Sassuolo), and the Pinacoteca Nazionale (Ferrara). The Galleria Estense is a collection of paintings, sculptures, and objets d'art (mainly dating from the 13th to the 18th century), which includes both works of art belonging to the Este family collections and works originating from churches in Modena and its surrounding area. The latter category includes several sculptures by Antonio Begarelli (1499–1565), one of the most important terracotta sculptors of the early modern period in Italy. Begarelli's monumental terracotta groups, still preserved in the churches of Modena, represent one of the most cherished and famous parts of the city's artistic heritage. His works in the Galleria Estense – around fifteen pieces, including fragmentary sculptures kept in storage – reflect this heritage in a museum setting. These sculptures also perfectly exemplify Begarelli's diverse production in terms of scale – ranging from half a meter to over two meters in height – and typology, from bas-reliefs to fully three-dimensional figures. Currently displayed as a coherent group within the galleries dedicated to the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries (mainly in room 12), Begarelli's

sculptures are exceptional in quality but present challenges in terms of display and public communication due to their conservation. All of these works have lost their original white painted finish, and in some cases, they consist only of fragments of high reliefs. By selecting two of Begarelli's works as case studies – The Baptism (inv. 4259) and The Lamentation (inv. 4260) – this project aims to explore the opportunities offered by 3D scanning technologies as a way for the public to engage with these objects in a new way, and as a potential tool for historical investigation, helping to reveal specific technical aspects of Begarelli's creative process.

Figure 3.1.1. Antonio Begarelli, Baptism and Lamentation, h. 75 cm, 1540 ca. Modena, Galleria Estense.

Figure 3.1.2. Antonio Begarelli, Lamentation, h. 138 cm, 1540 ca. Modena, Galleria Estense.

Begarelli made the Baptism and the Lamentation for the church of San Salvatore in Modena (Figg. 3.1.1-3.1.2). No archival documents related to this commission have emerged so far. However, it is most likely that Begarelli created these sculptures after 1534, when San Salvatore was completely rebuilt following a fire. An engraving by Giuseppe Guizzardi, dated 1823, is the earliest visual source documenting the original display of the Baptism (Fig. 3.1.4). Christ and Saint John the Baptist stood within a niche decorated with a canopy (now lost), while the circular bas-relief depicting the Dove of the Holy Spirit surrounded by ten Seraphims was attached to the rear wall of the recess above the two main figures; four additional Seraphims were placed around the Dove. It is unclear how and when the Baptism left San Salvatore, but it is certain that by 1906 the sculptures had already been in the Galleria Estense for several years. A photograph by Orlandini from the early 20th century shows the Baptism reassembled in the gallery, with a niche built to recreate the setting seen in the 1823 engraving. In the 1970s, the niche was dismantled, and since then the Dove and the Seraphs have not been on display, while Christ and Saint John the Baptist rest on a modern wood base placed on a high pedestal against the wall without any background (Fig. 3.1.1).

Fig. 3.1.3. Giuseppe Guizzardi (drawing), Giulio Tomba (engraving), Antonio Begarelli's Baptism, 1823 (from *Le opere di Guido Mazzoni e Antonio Begarelli [...]*, Modena, Per G. Vincenzi e Compagno, 1823.

Fig. 3.1.4. Antonio Begarelli's Baptism as displayed in the Galleria Estense, Modena, in the early 20th century (photo Orlandini).

The current display of the Baptism is visually misleading in several respects. First, it fails to evoke the original setting of the figures within a niche, and even more so the presence of other elements of the group that are no longer on show. Second, the two figures are now positioned at the same level, whereas – as is typical for this subject – the right arm of Saint John should reach above Christ's head, who is slightly bending to receive the holy water. The 1823 engraving clearly shows that the Baptist originally stood on a group of rocks, while Christ was on a lower level, his feet immersed in the waters of the Jordan River. Third, the current display exposes many parts of the sculptures that were not intended to be seen, significantly affecting their overall appearance. Begarelli did not create the Baptism figures fully in the round, but as very high reliefs, leaving large sections of rough clay around the fully modeled parts. This technique provided structural support, especially for projecting elements such as the swirling cloth around Christ. These unfinished areas were originally meant to be embedded into the architectural recess and then covered with stucco and paint, creating the illusion of weightless drapery. Today, however, these parts are fully visible and are the same color as the rest of the sculpture (in the 19th century, terracotta sculptures were often restored with a varnish that mimicked the color of baked clay). This alteration makes it difficult for the public to appreciate the illusory quality of Begarelli's work.

Finally, the usual placement of these sculptures within a museum setting prioritizes their aesthetic appreciation over the showcase of the sculptor's technique. Like any other sculptor working in clay, Begarelli hollowed out his figures from the back, leaving open holes to allow heat to escape during firing in the kiln, in order to prevent cracking. These holes are still visible on the back of the two figures of the Baptism, and through them it is possible to observe the metal wires the sculptor used to construct his works.

Describe the chosen technologies to be implemented

Different techniques of 3D scanning and photogrammetry were employed for the creation of 3D models of the two figures of the Baptism and of the Lamentation.

Identify specific challenges and opportunities

A 3D digitisation of The Baptism would yield significant results for both scholarly research as well as museum communication and storytelling. In particular, 3D models could:

- Allow a reassessment of the original spatial relationships among the sculptural volumes, especially the positioning of John the Baptist and the Saviour.
- Enable a simulation of the original white finish, restricted to the areas intended to remain visible.
- Provide digital viewers with access to the reverse side of the sculptures, offering insight into Begarelli's sculptural technique.
- Provide museum staff with full information about the conservation status of Begarelli's sculptures, allowing easier investigation of parts that are either non original or heavily restored.

Unlike The Baptism, the Lamentation has been preserved almost entirely intact. In this case, in addition to the objectives outlined above, the creation of 3D models would also facilitate a deeper investigation into Begarelli's working methods. In the Lamentation, the body of Christ is supported by three angels whose heads appear virtually identical. A digital superimposition of these three heads would allow researchers to assess the degree to which their three-dimensional shapes and volumes correspond. This, in turn, could support the hypothesis that the sculptor used a single mold for all three heads, subsequently refining each by hand once they were mounted onto the relief while the clay was still wet and pliable.

Consider the potential effects on the involved stakeholders (e.g., museums, local public bodies)

Once integrated into the online catalogue of the Galleria Estense collections, the 3D models of Begarelli's sculptures will allow for a better communication of these sculptures to the public in two different ways. First, with regard to their importance

and artistic quality, the perception of which is limited by the current images available on the museum's website. Second, with regard to the appreciation of their artistic technique, possibly leading to new insights in Begarelli's artistic process. In this way, this digital heritage strategy seeks to generate impact across multiple stakeholder groups, including both museum staff, art historians and the broader public

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

Detail the digitalisation processes

The workflow adopted and the data processing pipeline closely followed the guidelines outlined in Guidelines for the Digitisation of Museum and Art Collections (Bordignon et al., 2025), previously applied in the Digital Twin of Aldrovandi pilot study and in the Capellini core case study.

For the digitisation of the three statues, 3D scanning techniques were combined with photogrammetric survey. All statues were digitised through the combined use of the Leo Scanner and the Artec II Scanner, ensuring maximum resolution and accuracy in the capture of geometry. Photogrammetry played a crucial role in generating high-quality textures.

In the case of the Baptism, the statues were temporarily relocated from their current museum setting to a different space, allowing the operator to perform a complete circular acquisition around both figures. To represent the original placement of the two statues, the 3D models were positioned together within Blender software, and exported as a single .glTF file, in a configuration close to the original one, since the current display does not faithfully reflect it.

Figure 3.1.5. Placement of the digitised models of the Baptism as displayed in the Galleria Estense, Modena, in the early 20th century (photo by Orlandini).

For the Lamentation, however, this was not possible: the scanning and photogrammetric survey was completed in all accessible areas except for the back, which is positioned directly against the wall. The more recessed and difficult-to-reach parts were studied and integrated individually within the Artec Studio software. In line with the methodology and taxonomy adopted for the other case studies mentioned above, several versions of each 3D model were preserved: the RAW data, namely the data obtained from scanning and photogrammetry of the various statues; the RAWp, that is, the incomplete model, where the missing portions are clearly visible in the mesh created solely from the acquired data and therefore more strongly affected by the acquisition methods and spatial constraints; the DCHO, the complete model integrated through manual and semi-automatic methodologies; and finally the DCHOo, the optimised model, designed to be efficient and suitable for publication in real-time online interactive contexts (e.g. ATON framework). This approach allows for a comparison of the different resources and ensures greater transparency of the obtained 3D data.

In the case of the Lamentation, the RAWp version of the 3D model was used for comparison, as it features the highest geometric density and data entirely free from manipulations (without automatic or semi-automatic filling by the data processing software), for the purpose of comparing the heads of the putti in support of the art-historical study.

Figure 3.1.6. Digitised heads of the putti extracted from the sculpture Lamentation, oriented for overlay with the aim of historical-artistic comparison analysis.

The software employed for the comparison and analysis of the data was CloudCompare, a point cloud processing software. Specifically, the process involved the following steps:

1. Alignment and Registration

- a) Align (Point Pairs Picking): This tool allows manual selection of corresponding points (e.g., tip of the nose, chin, ear) on the two meshes. It provides an initial coarse overlap in cases where the meshes are significantly misaligned or scaled differently, and serves as a preparatory step for the subsequent ICP process.
- b) Fine Registration (ICP – Iterative Closest Point): Automatically registers two meshes based on point-to-point distance. This method is used when the models are on the same scale and were acquired together (e.g., using the same scanner or during the same session), as in our case.

2. Compute Mesh-to-Mesh Distance

The maximum distance threshold between the two meshes must be defined in order to generate a scalar field. Once applied, these values generate scalar fields whose visual interpretation is based on colors and gradient transitions:

- Blue/light blue areas = very high similarity
- Yellow/red areas = more pronounced differences

- The gradient (from blue to red) follows a numerical scale, which can be inspected through the SF display parameters.

For the data analysis, three metrics were taken into consideration:

- ICP RMS (mm) – Registration accuracy: indicates how well two surfaces are aligned. The lower the value, the better the overlap of the shapes.
- Mean Distance (mm) – Average deviation: measures the mean distance between the surfaces of the two models. A low value indicates a high degree of similarity.
- Std Dev Distance (mm) – Local variation: indicates how much the distances vary across different points. A low value suggests that differences between the models are evenly distributed, without local anomalies.

The analysis was carried out using Inverse Normalization, a method that transforms a value onto a scale from 0 to 1, where 1 represents the best possible case (lowest value) and 0 the worst (highest value). This approach allows different data to be compared uniformly, assigning higher scores to better values (e.g., lower error = higher similarity), while considering all three metrics with identical weight.

The formulas used are the standard ones for inverse normalization (0 to 1) and are suitable for converting quantitative values into a comparable index. The final results are presented in the illustrative graphs in Fig. 3.1.7.

Figure 3.1.7. Analysis carried out using Inverse Normalization.

Pinpoint what has not been used and explain why

In line with the WP3 guidelines, the phase of acquisition and processing–optimization of the 3D models has been carried out in full compliance with the established standards. The three models have not yet been published on the ATON framework, but their release is planned and will be detailed in the upcoming deliverables.

Conclusions

The 3D models of the Baptism and the Lamentation represent a new tool for studying the history, style, and technique of Begarelli's sculptures. The potential developments of this research unfold in three distinct directions.

The first concerns further work on the Baptism. Specifically, scans of additional fragments of the group currently preserved in storage (the Dove of the Holy Spirit and the Seraphims) could serve as the starting point for constructing a digital model of the entire composition, using Guizzardì's engraving as a reference to reconstruct its possible original appearance and to re-evaluate the spatial relationships among the sculptural volumes.

The second direction relates to the other sculptures by Begarelli held in the collection. Further scans could support ongoing research into his use of moulds. Scanning faces, hands, and feet would provide additional data for cross-comparisons among different works, further illuminating Begarelli's creative process.

The third direction concerns the relationship with the city of Modena and the surrounding area, establishing links between the works by Begarelli still preserved in local churches and those now in the Galleria Estense. For example, the Galleria owns two figures – Saint Bonaventure (inv. 3664) and Saint Pellegrino (inv. 3663) – which were part of a Crucifixion group still preserved today in the Church of San Nicolò in Bomporto, not far from Modena. Scanning the two pieces in the Galleria Estense, along with those still in Bomporto, would allow for a virtual reconstruction of the group in its original arrangement.

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